

Analysis Factors of Implementing ASN Electronic Performance System (SIEKA) Ministry of Religion Bengkulu Selatan Regency

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Abstract:- SIEKA is a management information system used to report employee performance. The application of SIEKA has been made mandatory by the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. All agencies under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion have implemented performance reporting through SIEKA. This study aims to analyze the factors of implementing SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. This research uses a descriptive qualitative method. Data was collected by carrying out observations and interviews with ASN employees of the South Bengkulu Ministry of Religion. The results showed that there were several factors in the application of SIEKA consisting of the support aspect in the form of socialization of the use of the SIEKA application and the provision of supporting facilities, from the capacity aspect in the form of operational funds, from the value aspect in the form of ease of reporting system, and from the additional aspect in the form of improving employee performance. In addition, there are also factors supporting the implementation of SIEKA consisting of infrastructure, performance allowance budgets, and applications. There are also factors inhibiting the application of SIEKA caused by the lack of discipline in South Bengkulu Ministry of Religion ASN employees in inputting performance reports on the SIEKA application.

Keywords:- Management Information System; Performance; ASN; SIEKA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Along with the development of science and technology, various agencies began to use various electronic applications to support work. The development of industry 4.0 has had an impact on the digitization of various aspects including the performance aspect. Employee performance in an agency will affect the quality and sustainability of the agency. An agency should have a management information system that can take care of various matters related to employees.

The system is a collection of interacting and well-organized elements. The interactions of these elements are interrelated consisting of input, processing, and output elements. In addition, the system is also influenced by the surrounding environment. The surrounding environment will

provide feedback on the system and this feedback is also called feedback. (Wahyudi, 2017:9). Information has meaning as a meaning or benefit. Information is deliberately recorded and structured so that it has meaning and benefits for the people who use it.

Information is a collection of records that are arranged so that they have benefits that can be used. While management is a process of certain activities to achieve a goal. The management process is carried out by managers or leaders to manage certain organizations or agencies to achieve goals. Based on this, it can be concluded that the management information system was formed to facilitate the process of processing information so that it has useful information for organizations or agencies. Management system information also facilitates managers in making decisions to achieve organizational goals. All agencies should have their management information system.

Regarding management information systems, the systems used in agencies are not only limited to education and training. Various other fields can take advantage of management information systems to facilitate work in these fields. Management information systems are used to carry out integrated supervision of management in areas such as finance, accounting, human resources, operations, and others (Hariyanto, 2016: 83). Management information systems are also used to accurately manage data such as employee salaries and inventory. Implementing a management information system can improve the accuracy of managed data because it is managed by a computer system. The next benefit can facilitate coordination where on an information system, information exchange management can take place quickly. This also helps improve the quality of human resources, with an employee management information system that must follow the existing system so that employees will adjust their performance to use the existing system. The management information system will reduce operational costs because by using the system management errors can be minimized so that it can help reduce operational costs incurred as a result of these errors.

Various benefits of management information systems are used by various agencies. One of them is in terms of employee performance reporting. This was implemented by the Indonesian Ministry of Religion in reporting ASN

performance within the Indonesian Ministry of Religion. The Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia issued an online-based application under the name SIEKA. The SIEKA application is intended for Civil Servants (PNS) or ASN (State Civil Apparatus) report performance. SIEKA stands for ASN Performance Electronic Information System Ministry Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. All ASNs from the Ministry of The Religion of the Republic of Indonesia are required to use the SIEKA application in reporting their performance by inputting the report through the SIEKA application. The SIEKA application can be accessed via the Website Ministry Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Work results are inputted into the SIEKA application to simplify the reporting process.

The application of SIEKA is carried out based on Circular Number: B-03425/SJ./B.II/2-bKp.04.1/2/2019 Concerning the Electronic Information System for ASN Ministry of Religion Performance. Each ASN is required to report performance through SIEKA. This performance reporting provides rewards to ASN if it is reported on time according to existing regulations. Payment of ASN performance allowances is paid according to performance reporting time through SIEKA, with discipline in reporting, ASN performance allowances are paid on time. For ASN who are late in reporting performance through SIEKA, the punishment they get is a delay in getting allowance performance. Payment of performance allowances will be adjusted according to the time of performance reporting by ASN. Performance reporting that is not done has an impact on not being paid allowance ASN performance until the ASN reports its performance through SIEKA. These rewards and punishments require ASN to implement SIEKA properly so that they can report their performance on time. This system should encourage ASN to do performance reporting quickly, precisely, and accurately.

A good performance reporting information system should have a positive impact on employee performance. Reporting on the performance of the South Bengkulu Ministry of Religion should have fulfilled its function in managing ASN performance data by making it an easy reporting process carried out by ASN. The use of SIEKA at the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion should provide efficiency and effectiveness to the ASN performance reporting process. Facility support-infrastructure implementation of SIEKA already should be available properly, so that the reporting process through this system also produces good reports. To find out all of these things, it is necessary to analyze the SIEKA implementation factors carried out by the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency.

The selection of the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion as the research location was based on the results of a performance appraisal in 2019 from a maximum of 100% to get a performance achievement score of 82.323%. The data was obtained from the results of observations at the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion. Based on these data, it can be seen the performance achievements of the ASN Ministry of Religion South Bengkulu Regency have been quite effective by touching a figure of more than 80%. This

indicates the success of performance reporting through the application SIEKA, while in the interview results, there are still problems in its application. The success and also problems that arise in the application of SIEKA are influenced by certain factors. The South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion, which has high-performance achievements by implementing SIEKA, can be used as a place to analyze these factors so that the data found and useful can be used as an example for other agencies in applying CHECK.

Based on this explanation, this study will look at a further description of the factors in implementing the ASN Electronic Performance Information System (SIEKA). Specifically on the application of SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. In this study, the description that will be seen is the understanding of the ASN of the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion regarding SIEKA, the factors supporting the application of SIEKA, and the factors inhibiting the application of SIEKA.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Implementation Theory*

Implementation is an action taken to achieve a certain goal. "Implementation is an action that must occur after the initial thought for something to occur" (Ehren, 2015: 207). Implementation is an action or activity that must be carried out after having a goal to be achieved. That meaning shows that application is a certain activity carried out to achieve a certain goal. Based on this meaning, in principle, the application is a way to achieve the desired goal.

Implementation activities are carried out to achieve the goals that have been formulated by an agency or organization. Implementation can be carried out if the decisions that have been previously determined are aligned with the goals to be achieved by the organization. Achieving the goals of each agency or organization has its elements according to what you want to achieve. According to Hambali and Suyadi (2020: 33) in general, the implementation has the following elements: (1) an agenda or program is being implemented, (2) there are targets or target groups that are expected to receive benefits from the agenda or program being implemented, and (3) there is an implementation of an agenda or program either from an organization or an individual who is responsible for managing, implementing and supervising the implementation process.

Implementation of the implementation should be done after fulfilling the elements that have been stated. This is done so that the implementation process can run well. In this study, researchers will analyze the factors of implementing SIEKA, which is a performance reporting program at the ASN of the Ministry of Religion, South Bengkulu Regency.

B. *Human Resource Management*

Human resource management itself is something science or how to regulate roles or relationships between resources (labor) owned by individuals effectively and efficiently and can be used optimally. It aims to achieve the common goals of an agency or institution. Good management of human

resources (HR) will have an impact on the success of achieving the goals of the agency.

Eri Susan (2019: 956) explains HR management which is a field management specialized in studying human relations and roles in an organization or institution. Human resource management includes the development, use, and protection of human resources. Marwansyah (2010: 2) states that the utilization of human resources in organizations is carried out through the functions of human resource planning, recruitment and selection, human resource development, career planning and development, compensation and well-being, occupational safety and health, and industrial relations. Various aspects of management need to be done to support the creation of quality human resources starting from recruitment to career development.

In this study, researchers will examine the application of performance information systems electronic (SIEKA) ASN Ministry of Religion, South Bengkulu Regency. Human resource management at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency is related to how ASN (SDM) employees carry out their performance reporting through SIEKA so this study will conduct an analysis of this. This is also supported by research conducted by Damayanti and Nina (2019: 397) regarding management information systems for SMK employee performance appraisal which demonstrates the efficiency and effectiveness of managing employee performance using an electronic management information system.

C. Management Information System

Management information system (MIS) is a system that is often encountered in various companies, organizations, and institutions. The definition of MIS itself is a planning system consisting of the use of documents, people, technology, and procedures in process management. This planning system is related to employee performance. Using this system makes it easy to manage employees within the organization. Therefore the use of management information systems is important in an organization/agency in realizing its goals.

The application of SIM in an organization/agency is influenced by three basic components including; organizational business processes (business process), human (human), and information technology (information technology) (Nasir et al, 2014: 476). These basic components become the fundamental factors application of a management information system in an organization. The first factor supporting the implementation of SIM is humans. Human means there are users or human resources who use the SIM itself. Furthermore, organizational factors are important supporting factors in the application of SIM. The readiness of an organization is needed for the application of MIS, from organizational infrastructure to environments. The last factor is the technological factor which plays an important role in the application of the SIM. Management information systems based on computer applications require qualified technology.

The application of SIM makes it easy for agencies to carry out management activities. Every agency should use SIM to support activities related to management. In this study, the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency implemented SIEKA for reporting the performance of ASN employees. The researcher conducted an analysis of the factors in implementing SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency so that what factors could be identified support the application of SIEKA which is a form of SIM.

D. ASN Performance Electronic System (SIEKA)

SIEKA stands for (ASN Performance Electronic Information System) in the form of an online web-based application. SIEKA is intended for Civil Servants (PNS) or ASN under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. This application is used to manage human resources to be more effective, efficient, fair, and aligned. In line with the objectives of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia, SIEKA is expected to bring about the application of a positive work culture to achieve superior performance from ASN. This application can also be used to monitor the performance of individual ASNs on a daily, monthly, and yearly basis. Furthermore, SIEKA makes it possible to measure the performance achievements of each individual and central agency by region and monitor the target achievement of the main performance indicators of the Agency. Analysis of the application of SIEKA needs to be done to find out how the process of reporting the performance of the ASN Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency using SIEKA takes place.

The application of digitization concepts such as the SIEKA application requires elements or aspects in order to be able to be successfully applied. There are several aspects that need to be considered according to research results from the Harvard JFK School of Government including; support, capacity, value, and additions (Jordan, et al, 2015: 82). These various aspects need to be considered in the application of SIEKA.

The support aspect relates to the support provided in the implementation of SIEKA. Application SIEKA support from the leadership is an aspect that needs attention. In addition, support from the Ministry of Religion is also an important aspect. Support is one of the important factors in implementing SIEKA, with a good support application SIEKA can run smoothly.

In agencies that are under the auspices of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia, aspects of the availability of resources need to be considered for the successful implementation of SIEKA. The resources referred to include various things ranging from financial availability, availability of technological infrastructure, and availability of human resources (HR) who have competence in apply SIEKA. These aspects play a very important role in the application of SIEKA, without these aspects the application of SIEKA will be difficult to use. Therefore the aspect of capacity is one of the important factors in the application of SIEKA.

The application of information systems is carried out to facilitate an activity process. At SIEKA this is intended to facilitate reporting on the performance of RI Ministry of Religion ASN employees. There is value in the application of SIEKA, this is an important aspect that needs attention. The value of benefits obtained by applying SIEKA are important factors to support ASN employees in preparing performance reports.

Additional aspects are aspects that are seen outside of the three previous aspects. In SIEKA, additional aspects are adapted to the function of SIEKA itself as an ASN employee performance reporting application. This aspect needs to be considered so that matters related to performance reporting support the use of the SIEKA application. These additional aspects include; employee work targets (SKP), daily performance achievement reports, monthly performance achievement reports, annual performance achievement reports, and additional tasks.

This study will analyze the factors in the implementation of SIEKA which took place at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. SIEKA implementation factors seen from the aspects include support, capacity, value, and additions. This analysis will provide information and data about the factors in implementing SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency so that it can be used as a reference for further implementation.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach, which collects information from facts that occur in the field. Qualitative research contains quotations of data (facts) revealed in the field to provide support for what is presented in the report (Setiawan & Anggito, 2018). This study focuses on the analysis of system implementation factors information (SIEKA) carried out by the ASN Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency to report on their performance as employees. The aspects of this research include support, capacity, value, and additions.

This research was conducted at the office of the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. Data collection was done by observing and interviewing. Observations were made by looking directly at performance reporting activities through SIEKA which were carried out by all ASN employees Ministry Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. Interview informants were determined using purposive sampling so that the number of informants for interviews was determined to be 6 people. Interviews were conducted with informants who consist of 1 leader and 5 ASN employees Ministry Religion of South Bengkulu Regency.

Data analysis was carried out using the Miles and Huberman (1994) analysis model as described by (Sugiyono, 2019: 321) which has the following steps: (1) data reduction, (2) data presentation, and (3) conclusions and verification. The data that has been obtained from the results of observations and interviews is reduced by summarizing the

data according to the research focus. The data is then presented in the form of narrative text in the form of a brief description. The last step is the interesting conclusion based on the results of observations and interviews that have been conducted.

IV. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

A. Implementation of SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency

The office of the Ministry of Religion of the South Bengkulu Regency Office is located at Jalan Pangeran Duayu, Pasar Bawah Village, Pasar Manna District, with the addition of the PLHUT building that was built in 2020. The South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion office is one of the thousands of work units of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. Led by the Head of the Regency Office of the Ministry of Religion (echelon 3), the Regency Office of the Ministry of Religion is an Office in the Regency that is directly under the Regional Office of the Provincial Ministry of Religion. As the Office of the Regency Ministry of Religion, the South Bengkulu Regency Office of the Ministry of Religion also oversees work units down to the District level.

On the internal scope, the Office of the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency consists of 5 work units namely the General Secretariat, Islamic Community Guidance, Catholic Organizers, Islamic Education, and finally the Implementation of Hajj and Umrah. The number of employees with offices in the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion office is 62 people, of whom there are 36 civil servants and 26 are non-ASN workers. Of the 36 ASN people, there is one leader, namely the Head of Office. Data on the number of ASN employees in the Office of the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency by place of assignment and gender is presented in the following table.

TABLE I. ASN EMPLOYEES

No	Place of Duty	Male	Female	Total
1	Head Office	1	0	1
2	Administrative Sub-Section	6	7	13
3	Madrassa Education Section	2	2	4
4	Diniyah Education Section and Islamic Boarding Schools	0	3	3
5	Islamic Religious Education Section	1	1	2
6	Hajj and Umrah Organizing Section	3	1	4
7	Islamic Community Guidance Section	2	2	4
8	Sharia Organizer Section	1	1	2
9	Supervisor	2	1	3
Total		18	18	36

All ASNs at the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion Office have implemented performance reporting using SIEKA. This was conveyed by the Head of Office Ministry Religion Ministry of Religion South Bengkulu Regency when interviewed based on Circular Letter Number: B-03425/SJ./B.II/2-bKp.04.1/2/2019 Concerning the Ministry of Religion's ASN Performance Electronic Information System stating that the use of the Ministry of Religion's ASN Performance Electronic Information System (SIEKA) can already be used per March 1, 2019.

In the 2019-2020 period, the development and improvement of the SIEKA application continue to be carried out by the Indonesian Ministry of Religion. Socialization on the use of SIEKA was also carried out, including the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion office. This socialization gives ASN the ability to operate SIEKA. ASN who already has the ability to operate The SIEKA was asked by the Head of Office to teach knowledge about the operation of SIEKA to all ASNs at the South Bengkulu Ministry of Religion. At the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion Office itself, the application of SIEKA will be mandatory in 2021.

All ASN employees are required to report performance using SIEKA. The results of observations show that ASN employees input performance reports ranging from daily, and monthly to annual reports. The process of inputting reports is carried out during working hours. On The process, ASN employees utilize the facilities and infrastructure in the office such as laptops and internet networks. This also makes it easier for the head of the office as the leader to assess ASN employees through the SIEKA system.

B. SIEKA Implementation Factors

Based on the results of observations and interviews that have been conducted and analyzed by the focus of the research, there are various factors for implementing SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. These factors are divided into several aspects. Following are the results of the factor analysis of the application of SIEKA.

➤ Support

The central Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia is committed to developing and maintaining the SIEKA application. The SIEKA application continues to be improved and perfected so that this becomes a factor that supports the application of SIEKA. The central ministry also provides training and outreach to regional offices including the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion so that there are ASN employees who can operate SIEKA, this supports the implementation of SIEKA for all ASNs in the office. In addition, support from facilities and infrastructure in the form of laptops/computers and internet networks makes it easy for ASN employees to report performance through SIEKA.

➤ Capacity

Availability of operational funds that support the implementation of SIEKA. Operational funds in the form of internet network payments and laptop/computer maintenance are always available so that these facilities can always be used by ASN employees to report performance. Each ASN employee gets 1 laptop/computer. Building infrastructure, electricity, internet network, and office buildings as a whole have no constraints and are comfortable to work so they support the performance reporting of ASN employees through SIEKA.

➤ Value

SIEKA can be accessed at any time, making reporting easier for ASN and neatly organized by the system. This system also makes it possible to see the progress of the performance percentage of ASN employees, called the Employee Performance Target (SKP), which was agreed upon with the leadership at the beginning of the year. Make it easier to classify the types of work from ASN so that the performance appraisal process can run more efficiently. Make it easier to manage ASN employee performance report data because it no longer needs to be done manually with paper but can be accessed in the form of a web database.

➤ Additional

The policy of the head of the South Bengkulu Ministry of Religion office requires performance reporting to use SIEKA starting February 2021. ASN employee performance reports through SIEKA are a condition for payment of performance allowance funds. This increases the application of SIEKA because ASN employees are required to report their performance through SIEKA to receive performance allowance payments. All reports ranging from daily, and monthly to annual reports can be viewed through SIEKA this makes it easier to assess the performance of ASN employees.

These factors are factors that influence the implementation of SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. The South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion Office can implement ASN performance reporting through SIEKA due to the support of these factors. The implementation of performance reporting carried out by ASN employees of the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion has been carried out well.

C. Supporting Factors

In its application, the use of SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency has supporting factors. The following are the supporting factors for implementing SIEKA.

- The Ministry of Religion infrastructure is very good in supporting the implementation of SIEKA.
- The obligation to use SIEKA from the secretariat general of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia makes ASN make a good effort to implement SIEKA.
- Performance reports are a condition for payment of performance allowance funds so that ASNs use the SIEKA application to report performance.

- The SIEKA application is well-systemized, making it easier for ASN to group reports according to the types of work.
- SIEKA can display ASN employee performance achievement presentation data to make it easier for managers to budget performance allowance to determine the amount of allowance for ASN.
- SIEKA uses technology 4.0 so that it saves paper usage because reports are in the form of a web database.

D. Inhibiting Factors

Application of SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency Owns some obstacles that sometimes arise. These inhibiting factors sometimes become a problem in the performance reporting process carried out by ASN. The following are the inhibiting factors for implementing SIEKA.

- The disconnected internet network application SIEKA cannot be accessed.
- Less Carefully ASN employees in inputting performance reports so that the results of the inputted reports do not match the expected targets.
- Lack of discipline in ASN employees in inputting performance reports through SIEKA which must be done every day so sometimes there are days where performance reports are not reported which results in a lack of percentage of ASN employee performance.
- SIEKA application only shaped web and is accessed via a laptop/computer so not too much flexible if there is a problem with the laptop/computer device because you can't be accessed it through other gadgets such as smartphones.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the research data that has been carried out, it can be concluded that there are various factors in the application of SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. These factors include the support provided Ministry Religion of the Republic of Indonesia with a commitment to improving the SIEKA application, providing training on the use of SIEKA to all regional offices, and providing facilities infrastructure to support the implementation of SIEKA. The next factor is seen from the capacity with the availability of operational costs to implement the use of SIEKA along with facility other supporters. Factors on the value aspect facilitate ASN report performance because SIEKA is a system that can display data automatically structured complete and neat. Additional factors that require ASN employees to report their performance through SIEKA so that they can be paid performance allowance.

The application of SIEKA at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency also has factor supports and inhibitors. Factors supporting the implementation of SIEKA are good infrastructure, an obligation that must be carried out by ASN, assisting budget managers in determining the number of allowances, and the form of a 4.0 technology system so that it is easily accessible. Inhibiting factors or problems that sometimes occur in the application of SIEKA are internet disconnection, inaccuracy, and inaccuracy of the discipline ASN employees in inputting reports, and the limitations of the SIEKA application which can only be accessed via a computer device. All of these factors are part of the SIEKA implementation process at the Ministry of Religion of South Bengkulu Regency. Based on all these factors, ASN employees of the South Bengkulu Regency Ministry of Religion have implemented performance reporting properly using the System Information Electronic ASN (CHECK).

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